

ISic1238

I.Sicily inscription 1238

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140723

1. Παφριανὸς Πάφι-
2. ος τῆδ' ὑπὸ γῆ
3. λέλ[υ]μαι, κωμω-
4. δὸς λιφθεις
5. τὸν βιότου στέ-
6. φανον.
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492841

EDCS 39101603

PHI 140723

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1238. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385651>